

SEARCH FOR NEW ANTISPASMODICS. PART IX

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The Mannich bases (II and III) have been obtained. The site of the Mannich reaction with the ketone (IV) has been established.

In Part VIII (this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 319; cf. *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1959, Part III, p. 153) the synthesis of the Mannich base, 4-phenyl-4-benzyl-1 piperidino-butan-3-one, its derivatives and of the secondary alcohol therefrom has been recorded. It has also been reported that these compounds possess some antispasmodic activity, though rather toxic. In this connection reference is made to the observation of Marshall *et al.* (*Brit. J. Pharmacol. & Chemotherap.*, 1952, 7, 85) that some β -dialkyl-aminoketones, chemically related to the above Mannich base, have been found to be spasmolytic, having non-specific direct action on plain muscle. In view of these observations, continued investigations dealing with the synthesis of such Mannich bases and their pharmacology appear to be warranted, and it has been felt desirable at this stage to have a methoxy substituent in the phenyl nucleus in such Mannich bases, since methoxy groups not only often confer enhanced biological activity but also greatly help in lowering the toxicity. Such a Mannich base, (III), has therefore been synthesised, following the same route as recorded previously (*loc. cit.*). Benzylmethyl ketone has been condensed with anisaldehyde in presence of hydrochloric acid (cf. Goldschmidt and Krczmar, *Monatsh.*, 1897, 18, 437 et seq) to furnish (I), which has been condensed with paraformaldehyde and piperidine to afford the Mannich base (II). On catalytic hydrogenation (II) has readily furnished the base (III).

A survey on the Mannich reaction indicates that compounds containing an active methyl or methylene or methynyl group undergo this reaction (Blicke, "Org. Reactions", 1947, Vol. 1, p. 308 et seq; Alexander and Underhill, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1949, 71, 4014). So far as the relative activities of these are concerned, it is found as a general rule that the methylene group is more reactive than the methyl group in a Mannich reaction (Blicke, *loc. cit.*), and this probably prompted the supposition that the methynyl group is similarly more reactive than the methyl. Based on the latter assumption, the Mannich reaction with 1:1-diphenylacetone was considered by Jilek and Protiva (*Chem. Listy*, 1951, 44, 49; *Chem. Abst.*, 1951, 45, 7987) to have probably taken place at position-1. However, through a series of reactions and also degradation studies it has been established from three laboratories (Protiva and Jilek, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1951, 16, 151; Wilson and Kyi, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 1321; Katz and Karger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 4085) that the Mannich reaction with 1:1-diphenylacetone takes place at position-3. These observations have now stimulated an enquiry to ascertain the site of the Mannich reaction in the case of a ketone of the type (IV), in which phenyl and substituted benzyl groups are attached to position-1. This ketone, obtained from the benzylidene

compound (I) by catalytic hydrogenation, has undergone the Mannich reaction with piperidine and paraformaldehyde to furnish the same base (III), as obtained by the unequivocal route (I-II-III). This has also been now confirmed in the case of the ketone (IV; $R_1 = \text{Ph}$) showing that in the present cases also the methyl group is more reactive than the methynyl, for the Mannich reaction.

Attempts to prepare the secondary alcohol from the aminoketone (III) by the use of aluminium propoxide¹ have failed. Probably some steric influence is involved.

($R_1 = p$ -methoxyphenyl ; $R_2 = \text{piperidino}$)

EXPERIMENTAL

1-Phenyl-1-(*p*-methoxy)-benzylidene-propan-2-one (I).—Anisaldehyde (41 g.) was dropwise added to a stirred solution of benzylmethyl ketone (40 g) in ethanol containing a few drops of HCl (conc.). After the addition was over the mixture was stirred for 5 hours and then refluxed for 6 hours. The reaction mixture was taken up in ether and washed free of acid. The solution was dried (sodium sulphate) and the ether removed. The residual liquid was distilled under reduced pressure. After a forerun of anisaldehyde and benzylmethyl ketone, a colorless viscous liquid (20 g., b.p. 218-20°/8-10 mm) was collected. On chilling it solidified and was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in colorless needles, m.p. 63-64°. (Found: C, 80.67; H, 6.41. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 80.95; H, 6.35%.)

The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 204-205°. (Found: N, 13.61. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N, 13.59%.)

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* was crystallised from butanol² in brown needles, m.p. 219-20°. (Found: N, 13.28. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_5\text{N}_4$ requires N, 12.96%.)

1-Phenyl-1-(*p*-methoxy)-benzylidene-4-piperidino-butan-2-one (II).—A mixture of (I, 18.6 g.), piperidine hydrochloride (15 g.), paraformaldehyde (3.6 g.), HCl (conc., 0.45 c.c.) and anhydrous ethanol (45 c.c.) was heated under reflux on the steam-bath for 12 hours. The solid obtained was washed with ether and then treated with excess of ammonia. The mass was extracted with ether and the ether extract washed with water and dried. Removal of the ether left a thick liquid (15 g.), which solidified on cooling. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in brownish stout needles, m.p. 86-87°. (Found: C, 79.41; H, 7.62. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires C, 79.08; H, 7.74%.)

The *hydrochloride* was crystallised from ethanol in colorless, microcrystalline powder, m.p. 197-98°.

The *picrate* was crystallised from ethanol in yellow rectangular plates, m.p. 161-62°. (Found: N, 9.92. $C_{23}H_{27}O_2N$. $C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 9.69%).

The *oxalate* was crystallised from ethanol in colorless, rectangular plates, m.p. 181-82° (decomp.). [Found: N, 3.42. $C_{23}H_{27}O_2N$. $(CO_2H)_2$ requires N, 3.19%].

The *semicarbazone* separated on long standing and was crystallised from methanol in colorless, microcrystalline powder, m.p. 219-20°. (Found: N, 14.13. $C_{24}H_{30}O_2N_4$ requires N, 13.79%).

1-Phenyl-1-(p-methoxy)-benzyl-4-piperidino-butyl-2-one (III).—Palladium-charcoal (10%, 0.1 g.) was added to a solution of (II, 6.3 g.) in ethanol (50 c.c.) and the mixture was shaken at room temperature with hydrogen at atmospheric pressure, when one equivalent of hydrogen was gradually absorbed and further absorption of hydrogen practically stopped. The catalyst was removed by filtration and washed with ethanol. The filtrate and washings were combined and removal of ethanol left a liquid, which was treated with HCl (dil.). The acid mixture was shaken with ether and the acid solution, when basified with ammonia, furnished the base, which was extracted with ether. The ether solution was dried (potassium carbonate) and removal of the ether left a viscous liquid.

The *hydrochloride* was crystallised from ethanol-ether mixture in colorless plates, m.p. 186-87°. (Found: N, 3.95; Cl, 9.68. $C_{23}H_{29}O_2N.HCl$ requires N, 3.61; Cl, 9.16%).

The *oxalate* was crystallised from ethanol in colorless plates, m.p. 161-62°. [Found: C, 68.48; H, 7.24. $C_{23}H_{29}O_2N$. $(CO_2H)_2$ requires C, 68.03; H, 7.03%].

1-Phenyl-1-(p-methoxy)-benzylpropan-2-one (IV) was obtained by catalytic hydrogenation of (I) over Pd-C and the method of procedure was the same as described above. The ketone, obtained as a viscous liquid, was characterised as *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone*, which crystallised from acetone in deep red-coloured needles, m.p. 255-56°. (Found: N, 12.98. $C_{23}H_{25}O_3N_4$ requires N, 12.90%).

When the ketone (IV) was allowed to react with piperidine hydrochloride and paraformaldehyde in presence of ethanol and a trace of HCl (conc.), according to the procedure followed previously, a base was isolated as a viscous liquid, the hydrochloride and the oxalate of which were found to be identical in all respects with those of (III).

1-Phenyl-1-benzylpropan-2-one (IV: $R_1 = \text{phenyl}$) had been prepared by Goldschmiedt and Krczmar (*loc. cit.*) by reduction of (I: $R_1 = \text{phenyl}$) with sodium amalgam and characterised as oxime. However, the following catalytic reduction is found to be advantageous: Palladium-charcoal (10%, 0.3 g.) was added to a solution of (I: $R_1 = \text{phenyl}$; 10 g.) in ethanol (75 c.c.) and the mixture was shaken at room temperature (ca. 33.5°) with hydrogen at atmospheric pressure, when one equivalent of hydrogen was absorbed and further absorption practically stopped. The catalyst was removed by filtration and, on removing ethanol from the filtrate, a thick liquid (10 g.) was obtained. The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p.

170-71°. (Found: N, 14.84. $C_{17}H_{18}ON_2$ requires N, 14.95%). The *oxime* had the same m.p. as recorded by Goldschmiedt and Krczmar (*loc. cit.*).

When the above ketone was allowed to react with piperidine hydrochloride and paraformaldehyde in the usual way, a base was isolated as a heavy liquid, the derivatives (oxalate, semicarbazone and hydrochloride) of which were found to be identical in all respects with those of (III: $R_1 = \text{phenyl}$; $R_2 = \text{piperidino}$), as recorded in Part VIII (*loc. cit.*).

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